

Multi-level Meta-workflows: New Concept for Regularly Occurring Tasks in Quantum Chemistry

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name	functionality
atomic workflows	
Opt WF	geometry optimization
Basic Opt WF	geometry optimization with small basis set
Freq WF	frequency calculation
TD WF	time-dependent DFT calculation
Pop WF	population analysis
Solv WF	optimization in solvent
meta-workflows	
Spec M-WF	spectroscopic analysis
Spec-Bench M ² -WF	spectroscopic benchmarking

Table S1: Spectroscopic simulation workflows (Fig. 6 and 7)

name	functionality
atomic workflows	
Opt WF	geometry optimization
TD-B3LYP WF	TD calculation with B3LYP
TD-PW91 WF	TD calculation with PW91
TD-TPSSh WF	TD calculation with TPSSh
TD-PBE WF	TD calculation with PBE
meta-workflows	
Opt_Bench M-WF	optical benchmarking

Table S2: Optical benchmarking workflows (Fig. 8)

name	Functionality
atomic workflows	
B3LYP-2 WF	geometry optimization with B3LYP and 2z basis set
B3LYP-3 WF	geometry optimization with B3LYP and 3z basis set
TPSSh-2 WF	geometry optimization with TPSSh and 2z basis set
TPSSh-3 WF	geometry optimization with TPSSh and 3z basis set
meta-workflows	
Geo_Opt M-WF	geometry optimization benchmarking

Table S3: Structural benchmarking workflows (Fig. 9)

name	functionality
atomic workflows	
B3LYP-2 Solv WF	geometry optimization with B3LYP and 2z basis set and solvent model
B3LYP-2 Disp WF	geometry optimization with B3LYP and 2z basis set and dispersion
B3LYP-3 Solv WF	geometry optimization with B3LYP and 3z basis set and solvent model
B3LYP-3 Disp WF	geometry optimization with B3LYP and 3z basis set and dispersion
TPSSh-2 Solv WF	geometry optimization with TPSSh and 2z basis set and solvent model
TPSSh-2 Disp WF	geometry optimization with TPSSh and 2z basis set and dispersion
TPSSh-3 Solv WF	geometry optimization with TPSSh and 3z basis set and solvent model
TPSSh-3z Disp WF	geometry optimization with TPSSh and 3z basis set and dispersion
meta-workflows	
Struct_Bench M ² -WF	structural benchmarking

Table S4: Structural benchmarking workflows (Fig. 10)

name	functionality
atomic workflows	
Opt WF	geometry optimization
Freq WF	frequency calculation
OptDisp WF	dispersion optimization
FreqDisp WF	frequency-dispersion calculation
meta-workflows	
Freq_Displ_Opt M-WF	gas phase optimization
Freq_Solv_Opt M-WF	solvent phase optimization
Struc_Opt M ² -WF	structural optimization

Table S5: Structural benchmarking workflows (Fig. 11)

name	functionality
atomic workflows	
Opt WF	geometry optimization
Freq-0K WF	frequency calculation at 0 K
Freq-400K WF	frequency calculation at 400 K
meta-workflows	
Equil_Calc M-WF	Structure optimization for equilibrium calculation
Opt plus 2 Freq M-WF	temperature-dependent energies calculation
Equil_Solv M ² -WF	Structure optimization in different solvents
Equil_Energ M ³ -WF	Combination for all complexes in equilibrium

Table S6: Inorganic polymerization catalysis workflows (Fig. 14 and 15)